

#5.1

Awareness raising, outreach & dissemination report

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Made4You facilitates the design of open healthcare through local co-design events and a global platform to share hardware solutions. Outreach and communication efforts are key and support every aspect of the Made4You project, including community engagement on a local and global level, improving the accessibility of open source hardware, making people aware of the open source way of creation and problem solving and fostering an ecosystem of DIY healthcare.

The Made4You partners have agreed on “careable” as the term for an open health+care solution, thus naming the dedicated platform Careables.org.

The strategy of how to move people of all target groups from becoming aware of careables to being informed and finally to actively participate is explained in the Engagement strategy (D1.1) that we consider the first part of our coordinated Community outreach plan, with this document being the second part.

Within the three years of Made4You, communication follows the iterative process the project as a whole adheres to, focussing during the first year on local community engagement and co-creation, the second year on global outreach and the third year on sustainability and exploitation of the results.

The report at hand provides a Communication Handbook for Partners and the Communication team listing main target groups, namely users, healthcare professionals and makers/designer; key messages like “Improving your Life in a Fab Lab”, “Open Source Hardware in Healthcare” and “People Centered Healthcare”. It shows the visual identity of the project, lists the channels and content strategy the project uses on digital media and in analogue communication as well as major KPIs for the outreach activities that will be reported on at the end of the project lifetime.

The Annex then provides very concrete working documents, like social media stats, templates and how-tos.

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
CONTENTS	3
List of figures	5
List of tables	5
List of abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Why: Objectives & Impacts	6
3. Who: Targets	8
3.1 The user target group	8
3.2 The healthcare professionals target group	9
3.3 The maker target group	9
3.4 Additional Target Groups	9
3.5 Contact database	10
4. What: Key Messages	10
4.1 Keywords	10
4.2 Naming	11
4.3 Claim	11
4.4 Definition	12
5. When: Timeline	12
5.1 Version 1.0 – local outreach and engagement	13
5.1.1 Waag (Amsterdam)	13
5.1.2 Makea / Fab Lab Berlin (Berlin)	14
5.1.3 Open Dot Lab (Milan)	14
5.1.4 Global	14
5.2 Version 2.0 – global & local outreach and engagement	14
5.3 Version 3.0 – Sustainability	15
6. How: Tools & Channels	15
6.1 Common visual Identity	16
6.2 Website content	17
6.2.1 News / Blogposts	18
6.2.2 Projects	19
5.1 Awareness raising, outreach & dissemination report	3

6.2.3 Events	19
6.2.4 Workflows / Coordination of content creation	20
Involvement of the Consortium Partners	20
6.2.5 Community Engagement with the Website	21
6.2.6 Dissemination of website content	21
6.3 Newsletter (e-Mail)	21
6.4 Social Media	22
6.4.1 Twitter: @CareablesOrg	22
6.4.2 Instagram: @Careables	23
6.4.3 Facebook: CareablesOrg	23
6.4.4 Hashtag #Careables	24
6.4.5 Content plan and activities	24
6.4.6 Tools	25
6.5 Print Products	25
6.5.1 Stickers	26
6.5.2 Flyers	26
6.6 Videos	27
6.7 External channels	28
6.7.1 Press & media	28
6.7.2 Blogs	28
6.7.3 Commission Channels	28
7. Events	29
8. Measure effectiveness with indicators	29
8.1 Quantitative monitoring	29
8.2 Qualitative measures	30
9. Summary and Outlook	31
Annex	31
Made4You communication timeline year 1	31
CI guidelines	31
Report Template	31
Website: How to create event posts & How to create blog posts	31
First guideline how to communicate more barrier free	31
Example for Social media engagement report	31
Newsletter Careables, 1st edition	31
Example for local Newsletter by OpenDot	31
Example Press Release, including analytics	31

List of figures

Project timeline, page 13
Levels of engagement, page 15
Logo, page 16
Website Landing Page, page 17
Website News section, page 19
Twitter account, page 23
Facebook account, page 24
Social media sharepic, page 25
Stickers, page 26
Flyers, page 26f.

List of tables

Official Colors for the CI, page 17
Project KPIs, page 30

List of abbreviations

CAPs	Collective Awareness Platforms
DIY	Do It Yourself
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement No. 780298 with the European Commission
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Waag	Waag – Technology and Society
WP	work package (usually with the number, eg. WP1, WP2, etc.)
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (en: Centre for Social Innovation)

1. Introduction

The aim of this report is to offer internal guidelines for the partners of the Made4You consortium, for the work package lead and for associated organisations who want to become part of or featured on the platform created within the project that is named “Careables.org” or who also use “Careables” as the term for their open health and care solutions.

This strategy takes into account three parts of awareness raising and outreach activities:

1. **Communication:** Information about the project and the topic to enhance awareness and engagement with multiple audiences
2. **Dissemination:** Information about the project results and related innovation to increase stakeholder acceptance
3. **Exploitation:** make results publicly available to enable uptake by other parties

The fundamental purpose of our communication and outreach activities is community engagement. As this is crucial for the whole project we have a dedicated Work Package on Community Engagement (WP1) within the project and created a separate engagement strategy document.¹

In D1.1 we defined the steps of community engagement that are the basis for reaching the right people at the right time with the right message. We also defined the broad target groups and framed the messages. With these parameters at hand, local outreach activities like event formats have been described in detail. The last part is the report on the first two open calls and their outcomes.

At every step of the engagement process, communication and outreach are key – on the global as well as the local level. The outreach strategy at hand will make it possible to address target groups, messages and channels more specific with concrete examples.

2. Why: Objectives & Impacts

Made4You facilitates co-design of open healthcare for people with (primarily physical) limitations. The project partners defined five specific goals with regards

¹ Please read “D1.1 Engagement strategy & documentation of events” before this document.

to community engagement, awareness raising and outreach when starting the project². The following paragraph indicates the outreach activities relating to the corresponding goal.

1. Build an **ecosystem**, linking existing local communities of citizens with disabilities and their families, healthcare professionals and makers and establish collaboration between these separate communities to develop their own open source and licensed interventions.
 - *for this purpose of the community engagement, local events and local communication are central*
2. Provide **access** to open source and digital fabrication tools enabling citizens with disabilities and healthcare professionals, in co-creation with designers and makers (DIY communities and makerspaces), to create customized self-made solutions to improve quality of life or services provided.
 - *the **events and open days at Fab Labs** that facilitate this access to tools are an integral part of the local and global communication activities*
3. Improve the **accessibility of open source products**; co-production of products that are tailored to people with special needs or disabilities as well as healthcare professionals and bypassing the limitations of the classical industrial production.
 - *a **central platform** is being built, to which open hardware specifications for reproduction can be uploaded, and which is also at the core of the global communication activities*
 - *the documentations of Careables (individual hardware projects) are disseminated throughout the outreach activities*
4. Foster the **ecosystem** through open exchange of knowledge, case stories and manuals. Within the DIY approach, local production and global knowledge sharing is key.
 - *global communication and re-utilization (exploitation) of local knowledge and products, with a special focus on the open source style of making things will be key to achieve this goal*
5. Build **guidelines** that allow anyone to replicate formats everywhere, considering the socio-technical aspects as well as relevant legal and

² Source: Grant Agreement, part A

regulatory frameworks, quality standards, IPR implications, security, safety and privacy issues.

- *these guidelines will be published and communicated to enhance the tool box of the global open source community and to make exploitation easy and likely*

All of the above will be broken down into concrete steps and work plans in the following chapters. These steps and work plans will ensure that the achievements of the project are used in a sustainable and open way.

3. Who: Targets

The main target groups for this project are patients, healthcare professionals and makers. Within the target groups we further differentiate groups with different needs and experiences.

3.1 The user target group

In a healthcare context, users are usually called patients. We prefer to refer to this group as “users” because many people within this target group do not consider themselves as “patients” in most of their daily lives. Being a “patient” has the connotation of having very little agency to many users, and also to many members of our team. In contrast, we believe in the agency of every user and in the positive effect that being actively involved as users in the co-designing of solutions can bring not only to the products that are being developed, and to the development of participatory design processes, but also to the users’ lives. These effects are augmented within the Careables context, as sometimes users are also makers or designers within the scope of this project.

Following the definition of positive health by Huber³, we also include emotional and social wellbeing into the scope of Made4You. Therefore, our users can be:

- people with healthcare needs
- their caregivers
- user groups, patient groups
- people facing physical, emotional or social challenges
- humanitarian support groups

³ Huber M, Knottnerus JA, Green L, Horst H van der, Jadad AJ, Kromhout D, et al. How should we define health? BMJ. 2011;343(4163):235–7. Available online: <https://www.bmj.com/content/343/bmj.d4163.full> (last checked on 17.12.2018)

3.2 The healthcare professionals target group

This can be:

- general practitioners
- doctors/specialists
- therapists
- nurses
- humanitarian support groups

3.3 The maker target group

Makers are a community of engineering and technology-based DIY practitioners who also utilize hacker practices, i.e. often combine hardware and software approaches to create new devices. Much of their work is focused on open source hard- and software in the fields of electronics, robotics, 3D-printing, metal- and woodworking, often implementing aspects of art and crafts.

The maker target group for Careables includes:

- makers
- designers
- engineers
- general innovators for generating ideas
- maker spaces
- maker communities

3.4 Additional Target Groups

In addition to our three main target groups (users, healthcare professionals, and makers), the project aims to build awareness on the topic of open and personalised healthcare solutions. Besides the general public, our communication strategy explicitly also targets policy makers and potential donors in order to secure long-term funding for the Careables platform, funding for projects in the wider ecosystem and funding for individuals who create careables.

Policy makers will be approached to provide the required infrastructure and prerequisites for custom grassroots healthcare products. In particular outcomes of the working group on legal & ethical aspects of the project (WP6) will be directed at the public sector target group to share and discuss the outcomes.

- The group of donors:
 - private corporations
 - foundations
 - NGOs
 - Governmental Organisations (all levels)
 - International Governmental Organisations (e.g. WHO, UNHCR, DESA)
 - crowdfunders > are individuals and thus also represented in the three main target groups
- policy makers
- public sector EU / EC

3.5 Contact database

In order to handle the different target groups in an appropriate manner, we create a contacts database that is only accessible within the consortium in the password protected nextcloud as it may contain personal information. It includes direct contact details of representatives, categories of the organisations and who is in contact with them.

All consortium members fill the table with people they meet, projects they come across and the status of the lead. The contacts database includes input from and feeds into the “Open Healthcare Map” (D2.1) that contains a selection of featured projects and solutions.

4. What: Key Messages

After having identified and further broken down our target groups, we defined key messages that are valid for a general audience and that can be used everywhere in our outreach activities.

4.1 Keywords

For creating our key messages, we identified and collected the most relevant keywords for the project:

WHAT: Innovation in Healthcare, Digital Social Innovation, Open Healthcare Solutions, change production process in healthcare

PRINCIPLES: DIY, Grassroots, bottom-up, people centered healthcare, respect social preferences, Open Source, low cost, internet of things, open hardware,

crowdsourcing, reuse, adaptation, customization, reproducibility, crowdfunding, co-develop (co-design, co-create, co-produce)

NEEDS: digital fabrication tools, open knowledge, open standards, mass adoption, ecosystem, solid categorisation

IS: safe, simple, interoperable, accessible, effective, timely, affordable, acceptable quality, personalized, open, inclusive, person-centered, legal, ethical

FOR WHOM: citizens, patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, users, innovators, engineers, communities, makers, designers, companies (Fab Labs)

4.2 Naming

One of the first issues the consortium had was the name of the project “Made4You” which many deemed too generic to be used in the long term for an open hardware platform on healthcare, as it can be used for any type of co-creation project. At the kickoff-meeting, we therefore decided to find a new name for the platform which would be acceptable for all stakeholders and target groups. The goal was to keep it as simple as possible, understandable, domains should still be available and a connection to health and care should be easily made – taking into account the different cultural preferences and associations with an English term. The brainstorming brought together a long list – and a good side effect was that the research also brought up more projects that the consortium can reach out to.

Finally “Careables” was voted as a name everybody could agree on. The similarly sounding “Wearables” has in the last years become a commonly known term for wearable technologies. We therefore assumed that “Careables” will sound familiar enough to not alienate members of target groups, while being unfamiliar enough to raise curiosity.

Finding a new name for our platform brought new challenges as we now use two names for the same project. “Made4You” will remain the official name of the EU funded project and we use “Careables” for all communication to the outside world.

4.3 Claim

Out of these word clouds we created simple & clear messages about the core of our activities:

- very short: **Healthcare made4you**
- longer for a flyer: **Personalised health + care products, created with digital fabrication**

We customized it also to target groups to cater for the specific needs and languages used.

- Patients: **Improving your Life in a Fab Lab**
- Makers: **Open Source Hardware in Healthcare**
- Healthcare professionals: **People Centered Healthcare**

As our target groups are extremely diverse in the wordings they use, are attracted by and understand, we always need to adapt our words again to fit the specific channel, prior experience, country or native tongue.

4.4 Definition

In a collaborative process that also included the feedback from our Advisory Board member Jon Schull, the consortium elaborated the following definition for a careable:

“A Careable is an open solution that aims to improve the quality of life for people with unmet particular needs or facing physical limitations. Careables are often co-designed, replicable, accessible, adjustable and shareable online using digital technologies. Careables is a relatively new category, that promises more readily customized solutions and a more horizontal and collaborative approach to health and care.”

5. When: Timeline

The Made4You project runs for three years and offers various milestones that are important for communication. As part of the co-creation of the project we also use an iterative approach for the outreach activities and will test different styles, channels for communication and addressing of target groups.

We divided the outreach activities in three main versions:

5.1 Version 1.0 – local outreach and engagement

- First year of the project, co-design and creation of the Careables platform
- Focus on local outreach and events within the partner Fab Labs and their communities and cities
- Basic website and social media activities
- Preparation of global outreach

The needs of the different target groups vary a lot and are in itself also very diverse. As it is a good practice to focus on a certain subset of the target groups with one initiative we do this in the first year with our three different Fab Labs on the basis of location, language and patient needs and also trying out different channels and content.

Most of the action takes place in the local meetups and open days as the co-creation needs small groups and focussed work.

To show what is going on in the co-design process, a few “behind the scenes” articles are published on the project website.

5.1.1 Waag (Amsterdam)

Language: Dutch and English

Patients: general public, on the basis that everybody does have some specific need that can be met

Makers: people who want to help other people in need, people who want to learn new skills, staff member from Waag

Healthcare professionals: Hospital staff through a special event within a hospital (Hackathon)

Channels: website, meetup.com, social media, individual events for specific purposes and the prototyping challenge as described in the engagement strategy

5.1.2 Makea / Fab Lab Berlin (Berlin)

Language: German and English

Patients: People with different disabilities

Makers: people who want to help other people in need, people who want to learn new skills, staff members

Channels: website, meetup.com, social media, word of mouth, newsletter

5.1.3 Open Dot Lab (Milan)

Focus on language: Italian

Patients: children and their caretakers as well as

Professionals: physiotherapists from Together To Go

Channels: website, newsletter, facebook events, social media

5.1.4 Global

Global outreach on the website and on Social Media Channels, preparation for bigger outreach when the platform is available.

Language: English, occasional languages of the partner Fab Labs

Primary features own initiatives and a few projects from Makers world wide that are relevant to the field.

5.2 Version 2.0 – global & local outreach and engagement

- First version of the Careables platform is available for outside contribution
- Execution of Global outreach campaign: Inform stakeholders about the Careables platform, show value to the wider community of potential participants
- Create more meetups beyond the three original cities
- Create sustainability strategy

With the availability of the public submission portal we start a global outreach campaign for groups and initiatives from the field of health making. We'll focus

on maker multipliers that we can reach with social media through featuring them and their projects on the platform and in our channels.

Using these examples from communities that are already empowered to participate we foster sharing to their wider circles and spread knowledge about the Careables initiative and Open Healthcare as a whole. Through this we hope to also reach people outside the circle as described in our engagement strategy (D1.1).

The goal is to ignite more Careables meetups in different parts of the world through publishing the how-tos, experiences and making co-design results available.

5.3 Version 3.0 – Sustainability

- continuous improvement of the platform, a set of documented projects is available
- Dissemination and exploitation of results
- Moving exhibition
- Execution of Sustainability strategy

6. How: Tools & Channels

This chapter describes our general communication and dissemination strategies, as well as the channels we use. The overall communications strategy of Careables focuses on direct exchange and talking to each other. All partners share the responsibility for the whole project and are finding a balance between communication and action together.

We identify the most important channels to reach the target groups.

In order to communicate the results of the project to the interested public as well as to ensure the wider project community is up to date with the progress of the project, social media and the project website are used. The project has a blog on its website with an option to receive a quarterly newsletter as well as presences on Twitter, Instagram and Facebook which are used to publish regular updates and relevant information form partners and other stakeholders, at least on a weekly basis.

We distinguish our strategy to fit three different types of communication: the project's own channels like the careables.org website or twitter account, partner channels like the instagram account from Wevolver or the OpenDot newsletter and External channels that we don't have any control over.

6.1 Common visual Identity

For all of the following channels we aim to be recognizable as Careables through a common visual identity and guideline for project partners and the wider community. It includes open fonts that can be freely used by everybody, a logo and colors that are easily recognizable.⁴

All products, design work and channel representation are based on this visual identity. In version 2.0 of the outreach activities, all fonts and design material will be made available to the wider Careables community.

The Careables design guidelines are added in the annex and include a responsive logo, colors and typeface.

The colors used for Careables are the following:

⁴ see Annex

primary color	secondary color	highlight color
clear blue	cool gray	bright orange
Pantone 2995 C	Pantone Cool Gray 4 C	Pantone 2013 C
#10a8e1	#cbcbcb	#ff9900

For the typeface we searched for open fonts that are freely usable by the community, are well established and very readable. The selected fonts are Open Sans and Sofia Pro Semibold.

Generally we aim for the design to be simple and modular. We allow and support iterations and adaptations to different needs by the involved communities.

6.2 Website content

The website **careables.org** is the central place where we communicate about our project online and make results available.

(Screenshot of <https://www.careables.org>)

The channel is controlled by the project team itself. With the website we reach out to all target groups that are aware, informed or participate and offer different formats for the different levels of engagement. GIG takes the lead in

coordinating content creation for the website and together with Wevolver is responsible for maintenance and updates.

The accessibility of the platform and its content is addressed as a key concern throughout the co-design and development as detailed in the evaluation and platform deliverables (D3.1 and D4.1).

In regards to content, the usability for people with visual impairments (like always add picture descriptions), broad use of easy language and translation of basic infos about the platform into different languages are our key concerns.

Sections of version 1.0 of the website:

- **Discover Projects**
Careables projects on the database (at the time of writing this report, the website links to projects which are featured on the Wevolver platform)
- **Share a Project**
Enables the upload of hardware project recipes and documentations to the platform (at the time of writing this report, the website links to the Wevolver platform)
- **News**
- **Events**
 - Event announcements for future events
 - Overview of past events
- **About Careables**
 - About Careables: describing the project
 - About the Project Partners: introducing the consortium partners
- Contact Option
- Option for newsletter subscription

6.2.1 News / Blogposts

These can be general announcements, reviews of events a consortium partner participated in, behind the scenes insights and Made4You project reporting, descriptions of projects aiming at co-designing products through Careables, general health making related articles.

In version 1.0 the categories are only visible in the backend of the wordpress blog software. In version 2.0 and 3.0 we will use the categorisation also to enable easier navigation and discovery of content.

Blogposts are written by consortium and community members, coordinated by GIG through an editorial planning document on the nextcloud.

Screenshot of the news section on the careables website; 13 blogposts in 2018.

6.2.2 Projects

These are results of co-design sessions, like photos and descriptions of tangible products (=Careables) created by consortium partners, individual makers or other organisations that give us the right to (re)publish their results.

In version 1.0 these are a few highlighted projects to give a first impression what a Careable can be. This part of the website will be replaced by the projects on the Wevolver based Careables platform that is launched at the end of year one as part of deliverable D 3.1. In the beginning of the second year a public campaign is initiated to create awareness of the platform and to start with engaging the global community.

6.2.3 Events

The local community engagement within the partner Fab Lab communities and wider circles includes a variety of events that are explained in D1.1. The impact of these community engagement events is increased by communication via website, newsletter, and social media.

In this section of the Careables website, we list upcoming events in the field of making, healthcare, DIY and open source which consortium partners are organizing, participating in or attending. In version 1.0 these are exclusively filled by GIG and the project partners. In version 2.0 there will be the option to accept submissions by the wider community to ensure the website is seen as a hub for a whole ecosystem.

6.2.4 Workflows / Coordination of content creation

GIG as communication coordinator provides workflows, how-tos and guidelines for content creation. GIG also publishes content on the website for all consortium partners if they need support with it. Particularly in the News section, GIG and the consortium partners create original content, like stories around the topic of co-creation in healthcare.

Involvement of the Consortium Partners

Each consortium partner has an account on the website and can publish information in their own name. GIG created a how-to document explaining how to post news and events on the project website that you'll find in the annex.

Each project partner nominated a person responsible for communications. In a monthly call, all representatives of project partners get together to share their activities since the last meeting and to plan the next months' communication activities. The meeting also serves as a reminder that all partners should communicate their activities, both internally and externally.

Reporting on communication activities is being coordinated by GIG with input from all consortium partners. This input has been brought down to a manageable amount.

One important part of the project's communication activities is harvesting of personal interactions: GIG developed a compendium (How-to) for project partners attending conferences or other external events. The goal is that we communicate a minimum of one photo and two sentences from each event any project partner attends, especially on how the attendance impacts the project, or vice versa. These harvested results are posted on social media (see below), and are often further developed into blog posts after the event. The compendium is being delivered in the form of an Email draft and GIG sends out reminders for the project partners.

6.2.5 Community Engagement with the Website

In version 2.0 of Careables.org, more interactivity and value for the community beyond the initial project partners are added as soon as the public contribution options are available.

Community members are encouraged to share event announcements in addition and potentially related to the careables projects which they share on the platform.

Added value will be made available through a “How-to”, e.g. on meetup organization and share formats from all consortium partners on documenting community or communication actions. To facilitate direct sharing on social media by community members, engagement tools on the website will be provided.

6.2.6 Dissemination of website content

In version 2.0 we will target not only already involved groups with the website but also use Google AdWords to direct traffic to the website for major campaigns, events, and announcements.

This will accompany our social media efforts to bring already aware people to the site and help them to discover projects they will find useful. With this we particularly want to reach the “users” target group.

6.3 Newsletter (e-Mail)

People we already reached with our outreach activities can follow the development of the project through a newsletter we send out via email. It includes news from all the different sections of the website.

The global Careables newsletter is sent out quarterly in 2019. It was sent out once in 2018 to announce the project and has 74 subscribers at the time of writing.

As the project focus in 2018 is local outreach, also a newsletter was sent out locally. The local Careables newsletter by OpenDot (in Italian) is sent out quarterly, was sent out four times in 2018 and has 318 subscribers at the time of writing.

6.4 Social Media

To create publicity around the project, project activities and the partners as well as to increase engagement with the relevant communities, the Social Media outreach on central channels are coordinated by GIG during the whole duration of the project. These channels are controlled by the project team and are used to reach aware, informed and participating individuals and can even sometimes reach unaware people through content visible to friends of friends and sharing.

All partners will use their organisation communication channels and social media as well to reach a broad audience. These channels vary a lot in followings and activity, as all the partners target different groups, are located in different countries or have different styles and preferences in their outreach activities. We also need to take into account that different features or channels are more spread in different countries so we adjust our strategy to the local needs.

With version 2.0 of the communication strategy, the Global Social Media outreach will be intensified as described below. This takes place mostly in English, with the partners' channels targeting people in their respective own languages. Project and partner channels feature each other regularly.

6.4.1 Twitter: @CareablesOrg

Twitter is primarily used to reach makers, designers, media and other professionals. The account posts original content, especially website updates, but also retweets consortium partners' posts, and relevant updates from the community to create a collection of information on open healthcare solutions.

Buffer.com is used to time content that will be shared across the week, like featuring communities, projects or other non time-sensitive content.

As Twitter is great for a lot of posts per day, we use the channel to report live from events. For this purpose, consortium members have access to the twitter and the buffer account so they can contribute to the tweeting where otherwise communication is centralized through the communications coordinator.

Work plan:

- around 12 posts a week
- Responding and engaging with fans and followers to build relationships

At the time of writing, the @careablesorg Twitter account has 223 followers.

6.4.2 Instagram: @Careables

Instagram is more for visual content. Photos, graphics (like event announcements) and short videos or live videos with hashtags and location (if applicable) are best to engage here.

Work plan:

- around 6 posts a week
- Responding and engaging with fans and followers to build relationships

At the time of writing, The @careables Instagram account has 77 followers.

6.4.3 Facebook: CareablesOrg

Facebook is used with a fan page for Careables.org that disseminates content from blog and website, posts photo albums of events and regular updates and relevant information from partners and other stakeholders.

As the facebook algorithms makes it tough for fan pages to reach their followers, the page merely replicates content from Twitter and Instagram. For major campaigns, announcements etc the payment of Facebook Ads (linked to Instagram) will be necessary.

Work plan:

- 5 posts a week
- Responding and engaging with fans and followers to build relationships

For events, the project partners create facebook events where Additionally, the project partners are advised to rather use facebook groups for community outreach in their countries/cities as these are still a very relevant way to interact and keep participants engaged.

At the time of writing, the page has 55 followers.

6.4.4 Hashtag #Careables

The hashtag is used by all consortium partners while making relevant posts.

During version 2.0 we ask the community to post pictures and videos with the hashtag #Careables. This involves people who already participate to reach out to their networks and therefore reach people from outside the circle.

6.4.5 Content plan and activities

As part of the social media strategy, different formats for sharing results and activities are created:

- short videos
- visuals, e.g. for testimonials from Careables partners and community
- visuals and graphics on upcoming events and campaigns

Example for a graphic social media sharepic

The activities on the channels will be adept to specific needs, but still will be organized with some basic similar concepts:

- Reposting / featuring posts by members of the community with #careables – thus creating our own hashtag campaign
- contribute to specific hashtag campaigns from the wider community, like #MakerMonday or #MakeSmthng
- use event hashtags like #rp19 or #fabcity
- make use of general hashtag campaigns like #ThrowbackThursday (feature activities from the past), #FollowFriday (Admin day: following people back, unfollowing dormant accounts, irrelevant accounts)

Social media toolkits are created and sent around via mailing list, slack or the open newsletter, depending on the level of the campaign. These snippets will make it even easier for the partners to post Careables updates on social media.

6.4.6 Tools

- Canva.com: create Shareable Picture/graphics to increase engagement
- Buffer.com: schedule updates for Twitter

6.5 Print Products

For distribution during events, several print products are created:

- Flyers
- Feedback postcards (shown in D4.1)

- Stickers
- Info Packs, Brochures

6.5.1 Stickers

For general outreach we created a standard sticker that is usable for all different target groups and countries. Additionally we have a more playful version that aims to be a fun highlight.

6.5.2 Flyers

The flyers feature nine different pictures to show the variety of Careables.

The back side gives a few examples and leaves space for interaction.

What are Careables?

.....

Personalised health + care products, created with digital fabrication. Like:

- *lighting for wheelchairs*
- *custom tricycles for children with neurological disorders*
- *3D-printed prostheses*
- *caps to seal used stoma bags*
- *pain sensing squeeze-balls*

Are you inspired by these ideas and want to develop your own?
Come visit us online or at our next meet-ups in Amsterdam, Berlin and Milano to join the co-creation!
Find the details on

careables.org

What is the problem you would like to find a solution for?

Careables has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 78029.

6.6 Videos

Different kinds of videos are needed for project outreach activities. In the first year we already created:

- Web video as web reel/introduction – created by Waag after the first Open Call series

During version 2.0 we focus on the global outreach and create short videos that show what Careables is about and how people can contribute.

To take social media algorithms into account that greatly highlight livestreams, we create Facebook and Instagram live videos as a recap on year one of the project and on the start of version 2.0 when we kick off our global outreach campaign.

In coordination with project partners, parts of events like meetups and presentations are planned to be live streamed to ignite similar activities in other groups.

In version 3.0 we will create a final video focussing on results.

6.7 External channels

All channels that the consortium can't control are listed here. These are channels needed for distributing the results and ideas and can be information multipliers, news feeds, portals, contacts with press + editors, TV, radio and much more.

6.7.1 Press & media

In order to achieve the second aim of this WP, broader public and media outreach will be necessary. To this end a dedicated press and media outreach kit will be developed, including visual and text based press material, press statements and blog posts to be disseminated by partner and other relevant websites. In addition, a press database will be created with relevant media contacts and journalists and media partnerships will be sought after, including media partnerships with leading publishers from the maker as well as the health community but also mainstream media. Media partners will be established which will cross-publish results of the project⁵. This part of the WP is coordinated by GIG between M1-M36.

Target group specific journalists are researched and contacted. With a first press release we contacted a wide range of international journalists within the Maker target group. In year two we focus further on the global maker press and acquire partnerships. As first results of the local Fab Labs are now available, the focus will be to support the Labs with press work and stress the importance of the dissemination to external channels through the communications group.

6.7.2 Blogs

Blogs are a popular medium in the assistive tech field and reaching out to bloggers is part of the journalist outreach.

6.7.3 Commission Channels

We use channels provided by the EC and other CAPS projects, like FETEX, CAPSSI, etc. to reach out to the wide European research target group.

⁵ T5.1.4 of GA part A

7. Events

The whole consortium continuously applies for conferences, speaks at events and therefore presents the project. The community engagement through events like meetups or maker gatherings is laid out in D1.1.

Each of the three hubs presents the Made4You ambition through 75 presentations and experience workshops on location.⁶

Made4You partners host engagement workshops at diverse events throughout Europe and occasionally world wide through the involvement of the GIG network.

To support event communication efforts, a common pitch deck is created in the beginning of year 2 after several iterations of what works best for which situation through the project partners during the first year.

8. Measure effectiveness with indicators

To monitor the effectiveness of our outreach activities, we collect and monitor engagement in quantitative and qualitative form. Besides the outreach KPI's we focus on meaningful interaction with the communities in the niche field of open hardware in health and care.

8.1 Quantitative monitoring

This part includes analytics, number of people at events, potential engagement & audience community engagement monitoring.

From our Social Media activities, we collect statistics via the inbuilt statistics features and combine them in a monthly report. Additionally we trace statistics twice a year for the project partner channels – who have all in all over 500.000 followers on Facebook, Twitter and Instagram.

For the website we track as minimal user data as possible as part of our data protection efforts.

⁶ T1.2.1 of GA part A

We decided on the following KPI's⁷ for our achievements after the three years of the project to be reported in the Final Dissemination and Sustainability Report (D5.4).

KPI	goal
Amount of participants involved in outreach to wider stakeholder groups on an EU and international level, in particular legal experts, policy makers and relevant public sector. This will focus on results from WP 6	1.000
The total number of meetup subscribers.	2.000
Presentations of MadeforYou Ambitions per hub	75
Regular open days specifically targeted on open healthcare	100
Total number of involved labs and makerspaces will grow	50
Development of mobile expo	1
Total number of Media Partnerships	10
Total number of Social Media Posts	1.500
Total number of Social Media followers	2.000
Newsletter sent out about Careables/Made4You	20
Total number of articles/blogposts on Careables.org	100
Total number of event announcements published on Careables.org	150

8.2 Qualitative measures

As part of the evaluation and impact assessment work package (WP4), feedback forms, interviews, face-to-face evaluation of the impact of the project is handled. We will use the interviews where appropriate as content for our outreach channels provided that the subject gives their permission. All details about this WP are laid out in the Impact Assessment Plan (D4.1).

⁷ These come partially from the Grant Agreement, partially from the community engagement strategy (D1.1) and partially from the outreach strategy.

Additionally, we receive feedback from individuals and communities in direct conversation, on social media and via email that we relay to the partners and that helps us to iterate our outreach activities, e.g. once we find out that a certain communication style works well or a specific campaign approach is well received.

9. Summary and Outlook

As outlined in the project contract Made4You has the vision to establish careables as the preferred platform for citizens all over the world to find open, intelligent healthcare solutions they are searching for. This highly ambitious vision needs a clear strategy on how to reach out to a large user community, made up of diverse stakeholder groups, and to gain visibility. We believe that the roadmap lined out in this deliverables and its supporting highly visual materials are appropriate. A close monitoring of the effectiveness as described in Section 8 above and an agile management of the different tasks allows us to react fast and pivot in case a certain measure or instrument is not performing as expected.

The timeline in Section 5 indicated the approach that we plan to follow for the remaining of the project, moving from a more local focus to a wider national, European and global outreach during the second year and concentrating on sustainability in the third year.

Annex

1. Made4You communication timeline year 1
2. CI guidelines
3. Report Template
4. Website: How to create event posts & How to create blog posts
5. First guideline how to communicate more barrier free
6. Example for Social media engagement report
7. Newsletter Careables, 1st edition
8. Example for local Newsletter by OpenDot
9. Example Press Release, including analytics

Hardware for healthcare

Platform that enables citizens to co-design and deliver people-centered health products through means of digital fabrication.

careables

**Please take your
time to understand
how it is applied so
that it will always
appear in a clear
and consistent way.**

Following pages outline a few simple rules about our brand.

Logotype — 06
Symbol — 10
Typography — 12
Colors — 14
Web — 16
Social Networks — 18

Content

These guidelines have been created to help other parties understand how to use careables brand.

careables provides citizens
possibility to co-produce
healthcare solutions that
quality of life.

The careables platform supports the connection made
between users, healthcare professionals and makers to start
the co-production of healthcare solutions.

careables

ens with the
t custom-made
at improve their

Content

These guidelines have been created to help other parties understand how to use careables brand.

Logotype

Official logo

The careables logotype is the most important element of our visual identity. It is the visual embodiment of the brand that people will instantly come to recognise and associate with careables project.

This logo is to be used for all printed collateral including all printed publications, advertising, billboards, posters, flyers and product packaging.

This is our logo to be used for all screen work, including websites, banners and presentations. Both these logos are available in a negative version.

careables

careables.org

Spacing

Logo Spacing

Always leave the logo some space to breathe. Use white or neutral backgrounds.

The word "careables" is written in a bold, blue, sans-serif font on a plain white background. The letter 'c' has a unique design with three horizontal bars extending from its left side.

Versions

Responsive Logo

A responsive logo is the term given to a primary logo that exists in several, slightly different and easily scalable variations. The need for flexible/ responsive logo design has grown with the demands of a digital environment.

The logo consists of a stylized icon of three horizontal bars of varying lengths, followed by a vertical line and the text "careables.org" in a bold, sans-serif font.

Symbol

Logo Construction

The symbol will be always used when

Center alignment

Positive Version

careables.org

Our typefaces

Sofia Pro Semibold

Originally designed in 2008 by Olivier Gourvat, this font family gives an impression of modernism, harmony and roundness. These nuances give Sofia a harmonious and sensible appearance for both texts and headlines. Redesigned in 2012, this typeface supports a wide range of languages with more than 500 glyphs.

This new version has also more OpenType features like case sensitive forms, contextual alternates, stylistic alternates, fractions, proportional and tabular figures. With its 16 fonts, Sofia is an ideal font family for text, brands creation, signage, print and webdesign creation.

Sofia Pro Semibold

ABCDEFGHI-
JKLMNOPQRS
TUVWXYZ

abcdefghi-
jklmnopqrstu-
vwxyz

Open Sans Regular

ABCDEF GH
IJKLMN OPQR
STUVWX YZ

abcdeghij
klmnopqrst
uvwxyz

Open Sans Regular

ABCDEF GH
IJKLMN OPQR
STUVWX YZ

abcdeghij
klmnopqrst
uvwxyz

Complementary**Open Sans**

Open Sans is a sans-serif typeface designed by Steve Matteson and commissioned by Google. According to Google, it was developed with an “upright stress, open forms and a neutral, yet friendly appearance” and is “optimized for legibility across print, web, and mobile interfaces.”[3]

Featuring wide apertures on many letters and a large x-height (tall lower-case letters), the typeface is highly legible on screen and at small sizes. It belongs to the humanist genre of sans-serif typefaces, with a true italic..

Colours

careables colours

Our colours are what give us our personality. We're bright, bold, colourful and confident. They're simply loud and clear.

Pantone 2995 C

Pantone Cool Gray 4 C

Primary color

Pantone 2995 C

C: 100%
M: 8.5%
Y: 0%
K: 0%

R: 16
G: 168
B: 225

10a8e1

Secondary color

Pantone Cool Gray 4 C

C: 0
M: 0
Y: 0
K: 27,5%

R: 203
G: 203
B: 203

cbcacb

Fonts and styles for online applications

Logo Construction

Open Sans Regular 10 pt
Text of the printing and typesetting Ninc industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever.

Homepage _____ **News** _____ **Events** _____ **About** _____
Line 3 pt Sofia Pro Semibold 20 pt

Hardware for healthcare _____ Sofia Pro Semibold 27 pt

Platform that enables citizens to co-design and _____
deliver people-centered health products through
means of digital fabrication. Open Sans Regular 17 pt

Searching for healthcare solutions? _____ Sofia Pro Semibold 18 pt

Discover open source hardware designs made publicly _____
available so that anyone can study, modify, distribute,
and make personalized healthcare solutions using digital
fabrication technologies. Open Sans Regular 15 pt

Discover

Line 2 pt
Open Sans Bold 15 pt

Social Networks

careables symbol

Beside the content we will use the symbol of careables as icon for all the social networks platform.

careables.org

This brandbook holds our
guidelines for expressing careables
through our product-styling,
branding and communication.

Design by Dani Montesinos Studio
www.danimontesinos.com
JUNE - 2018

STATUS REPORT

Date

Lorem ipsum dolor

Dissemination Level

Lorem ipsum dolor

Lorem ipsum dolor

Responsible Partners

Lorem ipsum dolor

Lorem ipsum dolor

Lorem ipsum dolor

Lorem ipsum dolor

Authors

Lorem ipsum dolor

Editors

Lorem ipsum dolor

Lorem ipsum dolor

Lorem ipsum dolor

Careables.org is managed by the Made4You project and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780298.

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CONTENTS

List of figures	p.
List of tables	p.
List of abbreviations	p.
1 Executive Summary	p.
2 Introduction	p.
2.1 Objectives	p.
2.2 Background	p.
3 Appendix	p.
4 Bibliography	p.

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 OBJECTIVES

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum.

2.2 BACKGROUND

Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua. At vero eos et accusam et justo duo dolores et ea rebum. Stet clita kasd gubergren, no sea takimata sanctus est Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

XYZ	XYZ	XYZ
VWXYZ	Lorem ipsum dolor	Lorem ipsum dolor
VWXYZ	Lorem ipsum dolor	Lorem ipsum dolor
VWXYZ	Lorem ipsum dolor	Lorem ipsum dolor
VWXYZ	Lorem ipsum dolor	Lorem ipsum dolor
VWXYZ	Lorem ipsum dolor	Lorem ipsum dolor
VWXYZ	Lorem ipsum dolor	Lorem ipsum dolor

How to Careables.org

- How to post an event on the Careables website 1
- How to post a blog post on the Careables website 4
- How to communicate more barrier-free 6

How to post an event on the Careables website

1. **Login:** <https://www.careables.org/wp-admin/>: Use your individual name and password
2. **Add new event:** click on “Events” on the left, “Add New”

3. **Name of event:** give the event a name that includes the most important information
4. **Insert event description:** describe what the event is about, explain unclear wording (e.g. not everybody knows what a ‘maker’ is)
5. **Enter tags, separate with commas, click “Add”:** tags are keywords that relate to overall topics (there is an autocomplete function and you can choose from the most used tags)

6. **Set time and date:** don't forget to adapt **time zone!**
7. **Give location:** some locations are already known from other events that were announced on the website, add a new venue if necessary (uses autocomplete)
8. **Choose organisers:** add a new organiser if necessary (uses autocomplete)
9. **Choose event category:** you can also choose more than one

10. **Choose a title picture for the event:** select a picture, either from your computer or the careables library
10. **Choose and upload a picture**
11. **Give picture a title:** that we can find the picture again if we search for it
12. **Alt text:** Describe image, this is important for accessibility (e.g. people with screen readers)
13. **Click "Set featured image"**

- 14. Enter URL of event website
- 15. Insert price or leave empty

EVENT WEBSITE enter URL of event website

URL:

EVENT COST

Currency Symbol: Before cost ▾

Cost: insert price or leave empty

Enter a 0 for events that are free or leave blank to hide the field.

ADDITIONAL FUNCTIONALITY

- 16. View “Preview” and then click “Publish” or in case you want to save it for later, Click “Save Draft”

Hi, Global Innovation Gathering

View preview

its calendar in place of the page.

Visual Text

publish

Status: **Draft** [Edit](#)

Visibility: **Public** [Edit](#)

[Edit](#)

[Move to Bin](#)

Tags upload

Separate tags with commas

- Hearables Hackathon
- Hearathon Co-creation
- Culture Hearing-Aids

[Choose from the most used tags](#)

imagine the future of
day life?

» To Hear« project at
to come to **Fab Lab**
starts on Friday,
» will publish the
fraunhofer IDMT website,
id careables.org. Join in

find the tonic fascinating:

How to post a blog post on the Careables website

1. **Login:** <https://www.careables.org/wp-admin/>: Use your individual name and password
2. **Add new blog post:** click on “Posts” on the left, “Add New”

3. **Name of article:** give the article a catchy name that is giving most important information
4. **Insert text:** in your article you can speak about a careables event that happened or one that happened within the careables sector, make sure you explain unclear wording (e.g. not everybody knows what a ‘maker’ is), you can also write an article about whatever might be interesting to read for the careables community
5. **Enter tags, separate with commas, click “Add”:** tags are keywords that relate to overall topics
6. **Choose categories:** This option allows you to choose the place of your blogpost on the website,
 - a. Select “News”
 - b. News are subdivided into: “Behind the scenes”, “Event reports”, “Health making” and “Featured News”
 - c. Whenever you select “Featured ...” your article will be shown on the homepage
 - d. It might help to check the website to see how other articles are categorised
 - e. You can also select more than one category

7. **Choose title picture for article:** select a picture, either from your computer or the careables library
8. **Choose and upload a picture**
9. **Give picture a title:** that we can find the picture again if we search for it
10. **Alt text:** Describe image, this is important for accessibility (e.g. people with screen readers)
11. **Click “Set featured image”**

12. **Click “Preview changes”** to check how the article would look like, check wording, etc.
13. **Click “Update”** to upload your article

rin. A colorful, creative group of of people with disabilities. The nt for new open source solutions y of makers and user experts will ater in the process.

y through all kinds of ideas for ur community members, but they already developed a few

How to communicate more barrier-free

Structure and design of content

1. **Headings:** subdivide text into headings, in the document (blog post / event post) headings have to be marked as headings. The overall heading would be marked as <h>, different subheadings have to be adapted to <h1>.
2. **Structure:** Most important information or a sum up of the content should be placed right underneath the heading
3. **Images:** All images on web site should have an alternative text applied
4. **Video and sound clips:** If there are, content should be made available in text form or subtitles
5. **Use of colours:** no low-contrast colour combinations, set contrast high

Language and formulation

1. Text should be clear and well written, short sentences, no loan words or technical jargon, if you use such wording, explain
2. Keep in mind: *Sometimes it is difficult to choose the correct wording when speaking about people with disabilities from the perspective of a non-disabled person. Don't forget: their disability is normal to them!*
 - a. Speak about people with disabilities, not about handicapped people!
 - b. Person xy uses/ relies (on)/ depends (on) the wheelchair, not Person xy is bond to the wheelchair
 - c. Person xy lives with/ has a disability, not suffers from a disability
 - d. Don't use the term deaf-mute, it's deaf

Social media engagement report - Careables - December 2018

Platforms

Twitter: @careablesorg

Facebook: CareablesOrg

Instagram: @careables

NB: December is the month prior to the start of the coordinated global outreach campaign and we shall use it as a baseline for analytics in the coming months.

Twitter

Highlights

	@careablesorg
Followers	118
Gender	62% male, 38% female
New followers	20
Tweets	10
Impressions	4648
Profile visits	85

Account home

Careables.org @CareablesOrg

28 day summary with change over previous period

Tweets

9 ↑28.6%

Tweet impressions

4,628 ↑20.2%

Profile visits

85 ↑254.2%

Mentions

15 ↑200.0%

Followers

118 ↑20

Tweet activity

Your Tweets earned **4.6K impressions** over this **28 day period**

Tweets	Top Tweets	Tweets and replies	Promoted	Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
	Careables.org @CareablesOrg · Dec 11	So proud we're part of this list! This week we'll be speaking at @republica Accra :) Join the #careables open hardware in health+care brainstorming at the health lounge and meet a few of us... And of course follow #rpAccra & @rpAccra & @ImpactHubAccra! twitter.com/WillSenyo/stat...		1,360	16	1.2%
	View Tweet activity					<input type="button" value="Promote"/>
	Careables.org @CareablesOrg · Dec 22	Searching for open source hardware healthcare solutions? Discover our collection today!		925	16	1.7%
	View Tweet activity	#careables #opensource #healthcare #technology #hardware #makers 3dprinting pic.twitter.com/ar8Cl654gs				<input type="button" value="Promote"/>
	Careables.org @CareablesOrg · Dec 26	From all of us, to all of you! Looking forward to a new year of even better innovations! Happy holidays ❤️ pic.twitter.com/GGo2JZSYbj		329	15	4.6%
	View Tweet activity					<input type="button" value="Promote"/>

Top mention earned 87 engagements

Geraldine de Bastion

@geraldine · Dec 28

Hardly ever experienced such a "it was so worth filling out hundreds of pages of EU tender forms" moment as right now watching [@CareablesOrg](#) and [#madeformywheelchair](#) speak about all the [#openhealth](#) innovations that have resulted from this project at [#35C3](#)
pic.twitter.com/wyMbKX51RM

🔗 6 ❤️ 15

Instagram

Highlights

	@careables
Followers	79
New followers	15
Posts	5
Impressions (total number of times all posts have been seen)	859
Reach (unique accounts that have visited posts)	344
Profile visits	56

3:51 PM ... 0.77KB/s 23%

← Insights

ACTIVITY CONTENT AUDIENCE

Emails 2
+2 vs. Dec 22 - Dec 28

Discovery ⓘ

307
Accounts reached from
Dec 29 - Jan 04

Day	Accounts Reached
Sat	0
Sun	55
Mon	60
Tue	84
Wed	63
Thu	120
Fri	98

Reach 307
+235 vs. Dec 22 - Dec 28

Impressions 732
+542 vs. Dec 22 - Dec 28

🏠 🔍 + ❤️ 📊

3:51 PM ... 0.93KB/s 23%

← Insights

ACTIVITY CONTENT AUDIENCE

Interactions ⓘ

14
Actions taken on your account from
Dec 29 - Jan 04

Day	Actions Taken
Sat	1
Sun	0
Mon	2
Tue	0
Wed	4
Thu	1
Fri	6

Profile Visits 12
+7 vs. Dec 22 - Dec 28

Emails 2
+2 vs. Dec 22 - Dec 28

Discovery ⓘ

307

🏠 🔍 + ❤️ 📊

12:27 PM 3.25KB/s 83%

← Photo

View Insights Promote

14 1 0 0

4 Profile Visits 71 Reach

12:27 PM 14.7KB/s 83%

← Photo

Searching for healthcare solutions?

Discover open source hardware designs made publicly available so that anyone can study, modify, distribute, and make personalized healthcare solutions using digital fabrication technologies.

View Insights Promote

18 0 0 0

1 Profile Visit 70 Reach

← Photo

[View Insights](#)

[Promote](#)

19

0

0

0

0
Profile Visits

94
Reach

Facebook

Highlights

	#
Page Likes	54
New page likes	3
impressions (people reached)	116
posts engagements (likes, shares, comments)	12
page views	24

Results from 8 Dec 2018-4 Jan 2019

Note: Does not include today's data. Insights activity is reported in the Pacific time zone. Ads activity is reported in the time zone of your ad account.

■ Organic ■ Paid

Published	Post	Type	Targeting	Reach	Engagement	Promote
04/01/2019 21:35		Boost Post				
03/01/2019 20:31		Boost Post				
01/01/2019 13:32		Boost Post				
31/12/2018 11:40		Boost Post				
26/12/2018 12:21		Boost Post				
22/12/2018 15:41		Boost Post				
06/12/2018 00:29		Boost Post				

Post Details
✕

Careables

22 December 2018 at 15:41 · 🌐

⋮

Searching for open source hardware healthcare solutions? Discover our collection today!

#careables #opensource #healthcare #technology #hardware #makers 3dprinting

Performance for your post

91 People Reached

2 Likes, Comments & Shares 🌐

1 Likes	1 On Post	0 On Shares
0 Comments	0 On Post	0 On Shares
1 Shares	1 On Post	0 On Shares

5 Post Clicks

0 Photo views	0 Link clicks 🌐	5 Other Clicks 🌐
------------------	--------------------	---------------------

NEGATIVE FEEDBACK

0 Hide Post	0 Hide All Posts
0 Report as Spam	0 Unlike Page

Reported stats may be delayed from what appears on posts

CAREABLES
open source hardware in healthcare

Check out Careables.org

EU project launches platform for DIY healthcare projects

Careables is an open and inclusive approach to healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making.

We see a big gap when it comes to commercial solutions trying to fill up for niche needs related to health & well-being: often they are too expensive, not very aesthetic, lack needed functions or simply don't exist at all.

There is a great rise of DIY Care initiatives that develop creative solutions with the help of digital fabrication like 3D printing in makerspaces. This can be lighting for wheelchairs, a custom bike for a child with disabilities or a special pen to help children learn to write.

With Careables, we want to

- create many more ideas like these and help to make them reality,
- accelerate the power of making the results openly available

For this, we're now starting to collect healthcare & wellbeing related projects from around the world on a single platform. Our goal is that everybody can find a solution for their problem, reproduce a project, adapt it to individual needs and also give back to the community.

Check out [Careables.org](https://careables.org)

Who is behind Careables?

The partners in this project come from 6 European countries and bring in their diverse backgrounds. They are

- [Zentrum für Social Innovation](#) (coordinator, Austria)
- [Waag with their MakeHealth Lab](#) (Netherlands)
- the [OpenDot fablab](#) (Italy)
- the [Fablab Berlin/Makea](#) (Germany)
- [Global Innovation Gathering](#) (Germany & global)
- [Wevolver](#) (United Kingdom & global)
- the [Centre for IT and IP law at KU Leuven](#) (Belgium) and
- the [Foundation Together To Go](#) (Italy).

What you find on Careables.org so far

Projects

We are starting to collect the first solutions: Pens with LEDs to help children learn to write, a 3D Printable Slithlamp and beautiful lighting kits for wheelchairs. [Find out more...](#)

News & behind the scenes

We continuously publish reports about our work so you can find out what happens at Careables beyond public events and results. You want to know how we co-create or test with users?

[Check out our blog...](#)

Events

We organize regular meetups with hands-on prototyping sessions and talks on making & healthcare – so far in Amsterdam, Berlin and Milan. [Join a meetup](#) or let us know if we missed any health + making events.

You like the initiative? Share this newsletter:

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Forward

Agenda

- France | July 14-22 | [#FAB14 + Solidarity: Democratize tools for health & solidarity making](#) & [#Fab14 main event: Fabricating Resilience](#)
- UK, Sheffield | Sept 4-7 | [Lorenzo's bike @ Design4Health 2018](#)
- Netherlands, Amsterdam | Sept 22 – Nov10 | [MakeHealth: Prototyping – meetup series II](#)
- Nepal, Kathmandu | Sept 22-23 | [2nd Humanitarian Maker Faire](#)

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Careables is managed by the Made4You project and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780298.

OpenDot 2018

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PERCHÈ CO-PROGETTARE

**La qualità del co-design è proporzionale
alla quantità dei post-it utilizzati!?**

OpenDot di ritorno dalla co-design session ad Eindhoven, felici quanto Mr Bean in questa foto!

La co-progettazione non è cosa da tutti e la ragione non è puramente organizzativa o metodologica. Certo, quando si co-progetta, le email si moltiplicano per gemmazione, trovare una data sembra un azzardo, ci sono obiettivi da mettere nero su bianco così come strumenti, poi si passa alla definizione del programma della giornata e degli imprevisti. Ma non è solo questo. **Co-progettare** significa creare uno spazio dove **tutte le opinioni, competenze ed esperienze contano** e servono, dove **si ascolta tanto quanto si sviluppa** una soluzione, dove **il progetto finale sarà utile** a qualcuno. Per questo motivo non è probabilmente il metodo più efficiente, in termini di ottimizzazione tempi–risorse, ma è sicuramente quello più efficace, perché produce uno spostamento di prospettiva e un cambiamento della qualità dei risultati. **“Nothing about us, without us”**.

CAREABLES MEETUP

Nuovo appuntamento questa settimana
Scopri tutti i progetti in corso

Miriam, Cristiana e Andrey scansionando il termometro durante lo scorso Meetup

Proseguono i Careables Meetup, gli incontri dove maker, designer, caregiver, persone con limitazioni fisiche e terapisti sviluppano soluzioni per problemi quotidiani. Sono comparse facce nuove e ci sono nuove richieste su cui lavorare. Nell'ordine:

/ **protesi per la piccola Chenuli** per permetterle di afferrare gli oggetti;

/ **distanziale per termometro** che avverta le persone non vedenti quando si avvicinano troppo a fonti di calore;

/ **oliera con led per ipovedenti** che faticano a distinguere il colore dell'olio e quindi a versarne la giusta quantità.

E se questo non bastasse, è in corso una ricerca sul tema della **mobilità accessibile** dove ci piacerebbe coinvolgere tutta la città!

OpenDot vi aspetta al prossimo Careables Meetup giovedì 29 novembre dalle 19.00 al Milano Luiss Hub.

giovedì 29 novembre h 19

Milano Luiss Hub for makers and students

via Massimo d'Azeglio 3, Milano

**NEI TEAM DI CO-DESIGN
FONDAMENTALI GLI INGEGNERI**

“Sono Chiara e spesso mi definiscono ingegnere human centered”

...non solo digitale!

“Sono Chiara, la più anziana dei Careables Meetup, essendomi laureata in **ingegneria elettronica** qualche decennio fa. Sono stata definita “**ingegnere human centered**” per la mia creatività nell’ambito tecnologico insieme alla mia forte sensibilità verso i bisogni delle persone fragili e l’ascolto delle loro esigenze.

Tutto ciò mi spinge a cercare **soluzioni tecnologiche per migliorare la vita delle persone.**

Parlo tedesco, inglese e francese e sogno di utilizzare da sempre le lingue nel mio lavoro. L’incontro con i progetti [Made4you](#) e la possibilità di partecipare nell’ambito del programma [Horizon2020](#) mi ha aperto la mente! La disabilità che più mi sta a cuore è quella visiva e **vorrei contribuire a realizzare una città più smart nei confronti delle persone ipovedenti”.**

LEUVEN

Il partner che si sta occupando degli aspetti etici e legali della piattaforma Careables.org

Erik ed Elisabetta nel cortile dell'università di Lovanio

Erik ed Elisabetta sono i ricercatori belga coinvolti nel progetto Made4You. La loro missione è quella di fornire una **guida continua** ai partner in merito ai principali **quesiti etici e legali** relativi al progetto, affinché lo sviluppo e la condivisione di soluzioni open in ambito healthcare possa avvenire in modo trasparente e sicuro.

Spazio CiTiP - Centre for IT & IP Law presso la **Katholieke Universiteit Leuven** (Belgio) è un centro di ricerca rinomato a livello internazionale per la sua esperienza nell'ambito della privacy, protezione dei dati personali e diritto della proprietà intellettuale. Il centro è composto da oltre 40 ricercatori, il cui focus consiste nel più che mai necessario **ripensamento dell'attuale framework giuridico alla luce delle rapide evoluzioni della tecnologia** nei differenti settori e ambiti di applicazione. CiTiP è caratterizzato da un approccio interdisciplinare, intra-ed-extra giuridico, costantemente in dialogo e con le prospettive legali, tecniche, economiche, etiche e socio-culturali.

NEWS

Il team M4U ad Eindhoven per uno degli incontri periodici

/ PAST- 23 ottobre

Co-Design Session a Eindhoven

A proposito di post-it. Durante il meeting Made4You di ottobre, Opendot ha guidato il tavolo di progettazione della piattaforma Carables.org. Un brainstorming di idee che servirà per costruire la nuova interfaccia partendo da zero.

/ FUTURE

#FuturaMantova

Tecnologie di fabbricazione digitale al servizio delle persone con disabilità: se ne parla sempre più spesso, ovunque e anche a Mantova, dove verrà creato un laboratorio permanente aperto ai maker proprio su questo tema. Il 30 Novembre all'interno di [#FuturaMantova](https://FuturaMantova), evento realizzato per il Piano Nazionale Scuola Digitale del MIUR, OpenDot racconta il progetto Made4You alle scuole superiori.

www.opendotlab.it / info@opendotlab.it

via Tertulliano 70, 20137 Milano / 02 36519890

Opendot è un FabLab e hub di ricerca e open innovation che nasce dall'esigenza e il desiderio di creare uno spazio per la prototipazione rapida, la ricerca e la sperimentazione. Opendot innesca cambiamenti che vedono nell'open source e nel know-how tecnologico opportunità di crescita a livello formativo, progettuale e produttivo.

Opendot è stato fondato nel 2014 da dotdotdot, studio di progettazione multidisciplinare che dal 2004 fonde arte, architettura, allestimento e design contaminandoli con nuove tecnologie e nuovi media.

/

Opendot is a FabLab and bottom-up research hub and open innovation with the aim to found a place for rapid prototype production, research, innovation and experimentation. Opendot initiates changes, identifying in the open source format and in technological know-how new opportunities for growth in the areas of training, design, production and research.

Opendot has been founded in 2014 by dotdotdot, a multidisciplinary design studio that since 2004 combines art, architecture, construction and design contaminating them with new technologies and new media.

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CAREABLES

Meet Careables.org in Berlin

EU project for DIY healthcare presents „Careables“ at re:publica

There are so many niche needs related to health & wellbeing which cannot be filled by established commercial solutions. That applies to the global north as well as to the global south. However digital fabrication and ICTs combined allow for co-developing open source (connected) hardware solutions that are designed for production in makerspaces to fill this gap – with many initiatives already working in the field of DIY care and producing useful and beautiful solutions.

The Careables mission: Healthcare for all of us and by all of us

With Careables, we're building an international platform to make it easier to document, find and replicate those solution, to highlight exciting projects and to facilitate new ones. With meetups and events in many different cities we're creating a learning community of makers, care recipients, and healthcare professionals to bring Do-It-Yourself care applications to the next level.

Find Out More

The Careables week in Berlin

The week started with the [first Careables meetup at Fablab Berlin](#), that brought together 25 people with special needs, makers, designers and other experts for creating open source solutions in the broad field of health & wellbeing. It was

the first in a series of monthly meetups. In these sessions Fablab Berlin will ideate and prototype related (connected) hardware products with you that can be replicated and improved in every well equipped makerspace in the world. Maker skills and/or experience with special health & wellbeing needs will be particularly helpful, yet everybody who wants to contribute is most welcome.

During the weekend makers and innovators from all around the world met at the Summit of the [Global Innovation Gathering](#). The internal meeting of innovation hubs and makers spaces from all around the world discussed Careables with a focus on documentation and humanitarian making, among many other things.

At [re:publica conference in Berlin](#), Careables present itself as part of the makerspace hosted by Global Innovation Gathering with a short version of the Fablab Berlin meetup and also hosts two additional hands on workshops:

- **Made for my Wheelchair:** [Building Open Lights for wheelchair users](#)

In this workshop with Isabelle Dechamps, Daniel Wessolek and Amélie Cayré you can learn how to build your own OPEN ° LIGHT for your wheelchair or another use case.

- **Peggy Sylopp:** [Hear How You Like To Hear](#)

In the workshop you are testing prototypes of »Hearables« (portable hearing aids) together with the Fraunhofer IDMT from Oldenburg.

All results will contribute to the global network that we are currently building with partner organizations and hopefully you on [careables.org](#).

CAREABLES
open source hardware in healthcare

Careables is managed by the [Made4You project](#) and has received funding from

the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780298. The partners in this project come from 6 European countries and bring in their diverse backgrounds. They are Zentrum für Social Innovation (coordinator, AT), Waag with their Creative Care Lab (NL), opendot (IT) and Fablab Berlin/Makea (DE), Global Innovation Gathering (DE & global), Wevolver (UK), the Centre for IT and IP law at KU Leuven (BE), Togethertogo (IT).

re:publica 18
BERLIN · MAY 2-4

One of the Careables Consortium partners, the [Global Innovation Gathering](#) (GIG) is a global network of innovation hubs, hackerspaces, makerspaces, entrepreneurs and innovators and since February 2017 a Berlin-based NGO.

GIG has been growing steadily since 2013 and now comprises of more than 180 drivers of global innovation from over 40 countries.

With its diverse members, collaborative projects and equitable setup, GIG is pursuing a new vision for development and cooperation based on equality, openness and sharing.

[re:publica](#) is Europe's largest conference on internet and digital society. It attracts over 9,000 participants to discuss themes and topics concerning our interconnected society and creates a space for bloggers, politicians, scientists, business people, artists and activists to come together. The founders of republica GmbH, newthinking communications and Spreeblick Verlag have been involved in internet policy and digital culture and society for over a decade. They are also the founders of two of Germany's most well-known blogs: [netzpolitik.org](#) and [spreeblick.com](#). The 12th re:publica takes place on May 2-4, 2018 at STATION-Berlin.

Press contact

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